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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning:

FEMaLe

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of 1 Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

1. ALL WP IMPACT MONITORING & ASSESSMENT REPORTS

12 out of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries have signed and returned the WPI informed consent form (75%).

10 out of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries responded to the baseline Pulse Check electronic questionnaire (63%).

FEMALE BENEFICIARY	RESPONSE (NUMBER)	ICF	MAIN WPs
AARHUS UNIVERSITET	Y (1)	Y	3,8,10
AARHUS UNIVERSITETSHOSPITAL	N (0)	N	6,7
EUROPEAN SOCIETY FOR QUALITY AND PATIENT SAFETY IN GENERAL PRACTICE/FAMILY MEDICINE	Y (1)	Y	1,9
SEMMELWEIS EGYETEM	Y (2)	Y	5,6,7
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	Y (1)	Y	4,9
SURGAR	Y (1)	Y	6,7
RIGAS TEHNISKA UNIVERSITATE	Y (1)	Y	4,6,7
KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN	Y (1)	Y	5
ISTANBUL AVRUPA ARASTIRMALARI DERNEGI	N (0)	Y	2
PRECISIONLIFE LTD	N (0)	Y	4
YOURCODE LAB INFORMATIKAI, SZOLGALTATO ES TANACSADO KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	N (0)	N	5,8
THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN	N (0)	N	3
CORRELATE AS	N (0)	N	10
NEMANJA TODIC PREDUZETNIK WEB BAY	Y (1)	Y	9
EGYUTT KONNYEBB NOI EGESZSEGERT ALAPITVANY	Y (1)	Y	2,9
THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	Y (1)	Y	3

Implementing Change

Implementing *Half Double* is implementing change. For the change to be a success, FEMaLe establishes a Half Double mindset with key stakeholders early in the process. This requires us to assess and rethink our current practice. We will build a Half Double mindset with key stakeholders early to change the current way we lead in the FEMaLe project. More specifically we will:

- Gather key stakeholders and project members to identify and discuss conditions to consider for building a Half Double mindset.
- Assess current mindset to direct change efforts and discuss practical prerequisites to support the mindset. Conclude on actions to be addressed.

FEMaLe Baseline Pulse Check Results

11 FEMaLers have replied to the baseline Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 10 out of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusions:

73% (8) are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score is 4,0 out of 5.

63% (7) believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score is 3,9 out of 5.

91% (10) are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score is 4,3 out of 5.

54% (6) are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score is 3,8 out of 5.

73% (8) are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score is 3,8 out of 5.

Flow

FEMaLe defines flow as *a project state in which the people involved find themselves in a state of high intensity, frequent involvement, energized focus, and enjoyment in the process they are currently engaged in* (see deliverable 10.1 FEMaLe Project Management and Implementation Strategy).

In FEMaLe, we define flow as a **frictionless stream of results and impact**. We want to stimulate creativity and ingenuity. To do so, we secure that everybody has an overview of the process, what the current challenges are and what will deliver impact.

Through mutual overview, we create the framework for optimum collaboration.

Leadership

In FEMaLe, we define leadership as **the ability to make the project happen** (see deliverable 10.1 FEMaLe Project Management and Implementation Strategy). This means that the leader can create a common vision which the FEMaLers can be enthusiastic about and which the stakeholders find appealing. Everybody needs to know the direction we are going, and they should be enthusiastic about the journey ahead.

Leadership is also about organizing the journey towards the goal and ensure that we reach it in a way that everybody feels good about. To make that possible, it is important that the project leader can release the team's energy and creativity so all the talents can do their bit.

In FEMaLe, the project leadership takes place on three levels.

- The project level: leading the project to impact.
- The team level: create a flow of results using domain knowledge to facilitate a people process and to energize interactions.
- The individual level: creating purpose and inspiration as well as providing continuous feedback through a competent leadership.

Collaborative leadership

In FEMaLe, we know that projects consist of people, not systems. Collaborative project leadership is about leading a complex system of human beings, embracing the inevitable uncertainty, and making the project happen.

A collaborative Project Manager (PM) can use domain knowledge to provide some of the answers in the project and to ask the right questions. At the same time, the collaborative PM can facilitate a people process with high energy in interactions to utilize knowledge from cross-functional experts, solving complex project problems in the process.

Impact Monitoring and Assessment Summary

All in all, the FEMaLe PMO is very happy to experience how the vast majority of the FEMaLe Consortium finds it stimulating, rewarding, and meaningful to be working in the project, enabling effective and efficient processes. As such, we are on the right track in realising a frictionless stream of results and impact (flow), based on collaborative project leadership.

Also, it appears that the FEMaLe Consortium is quite satisfied with how the FEMaLe Project Manager is leading the complex system of human beings, embracing the inevitable uncertainty, and making the project happen, especially facilitating a people process with high energy in interactions and solving complex project problems in the process.

Action Points

We will continue to have fun and act in an appreciative way to bring energy into every FEMaLe encounter.

We will show and communicate clearly about how each FEMaLer contributes to create early impact.

We will focus on improving relations, collaborations and deliverables by utilising Correlate FEMaLe and online tools (as described in deliverables 9.2 FEMaLe Dissemination Package and 10.22 Data-driven digital management platform).

We will plan and conduct interviews with FEMaLers about how the FEMaLe PMO may support their personal and professional developments working in FEMaLe.

These are the four top priorities before the next *All WP IMA reports* due M12.